

On the dynamics of Cosmological Singularity Theorems

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ABSTRACT

Since 1955, a lot of progress has been made in the field of Cosmology. More specifically, the idea of Singularities rose into Cosmology deeply with the introduction of the Raychaudari-Komar Singularity theorem. This was a great discovery, because although it only considered fluid-matter flow, it eventually led into the discovery of the importance of the Energy-Momentum density tensor in modelling the behaviour of *geodesic incompleteness*. The next immediate achievement was the 1965 Penrose theorem. Taking consideration of the modelling of the theta expansion already provided by the Raychaudari theorem and the importance of Cauchy Hypersurface relations to Space-time, Sir Penrose elegantly showed how you could understand the structure of Singularities by considering null geodesics all satisfying the expansion. Sir Stephen Hawking further improvised the theorem, by considering the importance of *closed trapped surfaces*. He eventually showed how geodesic incompleteness arises merely by satisfying three conditions: one, there being a closed *chronal hypersurface*, a set of light rays re-converging or there existing a closed trapped surface.

In this document, we will consider an analytical overview of the Hawking-Penrose theorem and its implications in Cosmology and the modelling of a “realistic” Cosmology model. Further, we will also side by side see how these theorems have very huge implications in Cosmology. We will also consider the Causal structures of these models.

We will consider also how the Hawking-Penrose theorem extends the original Penrose theorem and models the Time Reversal Singularity of a non-static accelerating Universe. Then, on a concluding note, we will briefly take a look at Causal definitions, and the implications of Closed Time-like Curves (CTCs), and how these are modelled.

1: An Overview of Singularity Theorems:

Spacetime was shown to be a Lorentzian Pseudo-Riemann Manifold. In general, a Lorentzian manifold is depicted as (M, g) . Here, after the birth of GR, the Einstein Field Equations, listed in the equation for the four dimensional spacetime, $R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R =$

$8\pi GT_{\mu\nu}$, showed something peculiar. The Einstein Field equations predicted the existence of a gravitational collapse that leads to a gravitational *Singularity*. Although Karl Schwarzschild modelled the first formulation associated with the structure of these Singularities, most of the credit for theorising a Singularity theorem is given to Sir Anmol Raychaudari. We will first define a Singularity:

Theorem 1.1: “A *Singularity* is defined as that point where a *Lorentzian Manifold’s* curvature becomes infinitely huge, and cannot be covered by any coordinate system”

Here, the last point is very important, because it helps us to distinguish between a “coordinate” Singularity and a “curvature” Singularity. For example, the event horizon, the collection of all points at a distance of $R=2GM$ from the collapsed star is a “coordinate” Singularity, and can be covered by the Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates, while the Singularity at $R=0$ is a *true* Singularity, and indeed all coordinate systems break down at that point. Now, we will consider the modelling of a Singularity theorem. For instance, in order to theorise a “realistic” Cosmological model, (consider it to be *non-static*) then we have to consider the following points:

- 1) Time Reversal Singularity
- 2) Homogeneous and isotropic (or anisotropic)
- 3) Division of the Energy momentum density tensor into terms for dark matter, radiation density and massive particles.
- 4) Total explanation of the splitting of the Cosmological constant.

While the second and third points are considered quite easily, the first point is an important result arising from the Hawking-Penrose theorem. We need to now consider Singularity theorems so far. The first on the list will be the Raychaudari-Komar Singularity theorem, which reads as follows:

Theorem 1.2 (Raychaudari-Komar Singularity theorem): “If the Raychaudari equation is satisfied along with the generic Time-like convergence, then the Energy density of a fluid will diverge in a fluid, resulting in an incompleteness of a vector”

The Raychaudari equation is the expansion of the Covariant derivative of a 4-vector. It has its terms in the expansion of the Raychaudari scalar and the satisfaction of the strong Energy condition. This was very important, because this was the first Singularity theorem, and furthermore, it was the first one noticing the importance of the expansion of a geodesic incompleteness, considering the Stress Energy Momentum Density Tensor.

We can also write down the following definition:

Definition 1.1: “A structure with a singularity is said to be (causal) geodesically incomplete”

We consider the following conditions for a singularity to arise in a model:

Theorem 1.3: “If a space-time model contains atleast one of the following conditions, we can consider the possibility of Singularities in that model: there should be an incompatible set of Energy and Causal conditions, this leads to geodesic incompleteness”

The Pattern Singularity theorem is theorem 1.3 along with another condition: there should also be a set of initial or boundary conditions, which produce these incompleteness. We can state the Pattern Singularity theorem as:

Theorem 1.4: *“If a space-time model contains solutions which show conditions satisfying theorem 1.3 and also shows the presence of initial conditions showing similarities, we can conclude that it can house geodesic incompleteness”*

This was the first Singularity theorem showing the importance of Causal conditioning in a structure containing geodesic incompleteness. The mathematical essence of a Singularity can now be modelled by considering the importance of the weak, strong, and the generic Energy Conditions (ECs). The following three definitions will be used to model the Penrose theorem.

Definition 1.2 (Weak Energy Condition): *“If a model is such that we can simply state $T_{\mu\nu}v^\mu v^\nu \geq 0$, then it is said to satisfy the weak Energy Condition”*

Definition 1.3 (Strong Energy Condition): *“If a model is such that the trace of the Energy Momentum Density Tensor is comparable, and the difference of the Tensor and its trace multiplied by a half of the metric tensor times the product of the vector in its tuples is non-negative, then it is said to satisfy the strong Energy Condition. Mathematically, if it satisfies $(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Tg_{\mu\nu})v^\mu v^\nu \geq 0$, it is said to satisfy the strong Energy Condition, where T is the trace of the Stress-Energy-Momentum-density Tensor”*

Definition 1.4 (Generic Energy Condition): *“If a model is such that it satisfies the relation $R_{\alpha\beta\gamma\mu}v^\mu v^\nu \geq 0$, then it is said to satisfy the generic Energy Condition”*

With these definitions set, we can now introduce ourselves to the idea of a Closed Trapped Surface.

A Closed Trapped Surface can be defined by the statement, “draw a sphere, then a plane tangential to it at a point “p” , then by drawing the perpendicular to it. This gives the normal basis to the sphere “M” and then considering the light rays convergence. If both the ingoing light rays from any two points on M and the outgoing light rays from M converge, then we say that this is a *Closed Trapped Surface*” . This we have defined for a Space-like compact M. Also, a Cauchy Hypersurface is the “good space, time-slices” on M. So now that the initial values are satisfied, thereby satisfying the basis of a Singularity theorem, we can now define the 1965 Penrose theorem.

Theorem 1.5 (Penrose Theorem): *“If a space-time model is such that there exists a non-compact Cauchy Hypersurface and a Closed Trapped Surface, and if all null geodesics satisfy the Time-like convergence condition along with the Raychaudari expansion, then there exists a geodesic incompleteness in that structure”*

A key point over here is that the Raychaudari expansion, defined from the following two equations, $\theta = \nabla_\mu v^\mu$ satisfies $\dot{\theta} = -\sigma_{\mu\nu}\sigma^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{3}\theta^2 - E(|V|)_\mu^\mu$, leading to the Hawking-Penrose theorem. Here, σ denotes the shear tensor, while $E(|V|)_\mu^\mu$ satisfies the Raychaudari scalar, the Einstein Field Equations and the condition that it proves true for the strong Energy Condition being Time-like. Also, it consider the importance of a Closed Trapped Surface, and the Cauchy Hypersurface relations.

As we will see, the Penrose theorem paved way for the Hawking-Penrose theorem, which

has a very deep impact in Cosmology. Sir Stephen Hawking showed beautifully how a non-static accelerating Universe, when its arrow of time is reversed forms a structure satisfying the original Penrose theorem, proving that the Universe, began from a Singularity.

2: The Hawking-Penrose theorem:

2.1: The theorem:

The original Cosmological models were based upon the assumption the Universe *did* have a beginning. The nature of it, though was unknown. The three models proposed by Alexander Friedmann showed this assumption very clearly, however what form, or what mathematical nature it had was unknown, until the general Singularity theorems showed how you could model surfaces with the possibility of geodesic incompleteness. After Sir Roger Penrose proposed his theorem in 1965, Sir Stephen Hawking thought what it would be, if you reversed the arrow of time. Now, a Trapped Surface forms if gravity is strong enough for any light rays both ingoing and outgoing from the surface of M , and as we know it, gravity would become stronger if you reversed the arrow of time for a forever expanding Universe. This meant, that there would be the possibility that if you reversed the arrow of time for an expanding Universe, it should contract instead, thereby meaning that gravity was strong to form a Trapped Surface. Stephen Hawking showed that if you reversed the arrow of time, there is the formation of a Singularity. In other words, as you reversed the arrow of time, gravity can be thought to be able to form a Trapped Surface, thereby satisfying the most crucial condition for the formation of a geodesic incompleteness for a space-time model. If the Raychaudari expansion is satisfied along with the Energy Conditions, then we can consider it to be in the possibility to model geodesic incompleteness for the Penrose theorem. If, along with them there is the key elements of a (for a simple version of the original theorem) compact Space-like Hypersurface and a Closed Trapped Surface, but under Time Reversal condition, then this categorises that space-time structure to model geodesic incompleteness. Combining all these conditions, we define the Hawking-Penrose theorem as:

Theorem 2.1.1 (Hawking-Penrose theorem): *“If a space-time structure is such that under Time Reversal it forms a Trapped Surface Σ , and is taken along the Cauchy Hypersurface Γ , and forms a model satisfying the original Penrose theorem, then it is equipped with a geodesic incompleteness, labelled as a Time Reversal Singularity, provided the model does not contain CTCs”*

This shows that the origin of the Universe was from a Singularity. This is of an extraordinary importance. It shows that the Universe originated from a singular point, defined to be the infinite curvature of space-time. (A point which is important is that the class C^2 , $C^{1.1}$ is the natural arena of Singularity theorems we have discussed here. Also, these theorems also consider these variations under high degrees of symmetry).

2.2: Further: Closed Time-like Curves:

The world-lines of massive particles are defined to be Time-like. Further, the Causal

condition is defined as the following definition:

Definition 2.2.1 (Causal conditions): “*The Causal conditions are defined as the set of principle that both prevent a particle from tracing its past, and maximises the length of proper time along any two neighbouring events*”

The following definitions further describe causal curves and directions:

Definition 2.2.2: “*The Time-like future of a point $p \in M$ is the collection of all points $q \in M$ such that a future directed Time-like curve exists that joins p and q . This is represented as I^+* ”

Definition 2.2.3: “*The Causal future of a point $p \in M$ is the collection of all points $q \in M$ such that a future directed Causal curve joins p and q . This is represented as J^+* ”

Definition 2.2.4: “*A horismosis relation exists between two events p and q if they can be joined via a future light-like curve. This is depicted as $p \rightarrow q$. Further, we can define Chronological precedence and Causal precedence. Chronological precedence is when p and q can be joined via a Time-like future curve, depicted as $p \ll q$. Causal precedence is when they can be joined via a Causal future directed curve*”

These definitions are very important to define the Causal structure of a structure. For instance, we can form the Causal structure of the Time reversal Singularity by these definitions. CTCs are defined using Chronological violations, which means that they are defined on the very basic intuition defined by these definitions. The first model to contain CTCs is the Van Stockum model, given by Jacob Van Stockum.

A certain model, labelled as the Van Stockum model considered one of the first structures in General Relativity showing a slight violation of the Causal condition. The model was you had an infinitely long cylinder of rotating dust. Considering Cylindrical symmetry, if you had the product of the angular velocity and the radius of the cylinder greater than c , then the Van Stockum metric showed that there would be Closed Time-like Curves (CTCs) arising. Kurt Godel showed later that the idea was actually important, because a model satisfying the weak Energy Condition can house CTCs. This was incorporated in his model of Universe, which satisfied the Einstein Field Equations and showed that CTCs were important in Cosmology (also, the Godel Universe model is not globally hyperbolic). Another very important example is the Misner model, wherein CTCs are modelled.

CTCs are very important, because the Hawking-Penrose theorem itself predicts that CTCs should arise from a “realistic” Cosmological model. For example, a realistic model would be one that both considers the Hawking-Penrose theorem if it is considering a non-static accelerating universe, and also considers all of the Energy Conditions. Also, they have a lot of implications. Firstly, CTCs show that there exists some model housing some form of violation of the Causal principles. Secondly, this also means that a model providing exact solutions to the Einstein Field Equations can include a causal paradox, meaning that a causal loop may exist.

CONCLUSION

In this document we have considered the various Singularity theorems and have captured the basic structure of these theorems in a nutshell. Also, we have seen the basic definitions that underlie the important assumptions and points behind the concept of a Singularity. We have also taken into consideration the important propositions playing the key role of geodesic incompleteness. We have read through the conditions needed to be satisfied by a model so that we can theorise Singularity theorems, namely the importance of Cauchy Hypersurface, a Trapped Surface, and the three Energy Conditions, the strong, weak and the generic conditions. We have considered the Raychaudari Singularity, Pattern Singularity, the Penrose Singularity and the Hawking-Penrose theorem, the four very important theorems in Cosmology that define the most important steps to answering the most fundamental question, “what is the nature of the beginning of the Universe” .

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